

Equivalent Units of Production in Unit Cost Calculation for Fair Pricing of Pharmaceuticals: A Scoping Review Protocol

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this scoping review is to examine extant evidence and escalate conversation towards building a critical mass in literature on equivalent unit of production, unit cost function, continuous process costing and fair pricing in the pharmaceutical industry. The main aim is to clarify concepts and provide direction for subsequent empirical studies.

Introduction: Insufficient consideration has been given in pharmaceutical pricing conversations to underlying unit cost function, equivalent unit of production and fair pricing concepts respectively. Because regardless of pricing orientation, Drury (2021, p.242) asserts that ‘the cost of the product provides the initial approximation of the selling price’.

Inclusion criteria: Studies will be included on equivalent units of production, (process) costing, unit costing, target costing and fair pricing in the pharmaceutical industry respectively as participants and concepts in the context of fair pricing of pharmaceuticals. Secondly, abstract and complete text in English language will also be included. However, studies on these concepts outside the industry will be excluded.

Methods: Searches without time limit will be conducted on Google scholar, Web of Science, and gray literature to optimize the number of relevant articles. Subject headings will include equivalent units/, equivalent production/, process costing/ unit costing/costing practices/fair pricing/and, pharmaceuticals. Reference lists of relevant articles will be further screened. All citations will be imported into the Zotero Reference Manager to remove duplicates. One reviewer will conduct data extraction process, while another will cross-check. Data will be tabulated and accompanied by a narrative summary in line with the study’s objectives.

Key words: Equivalent units of production; fair pricing; pharmaceuticals; unit cost of production, scoping review, protocol

JEL CLASSIFICATION: I18, M4, M21, L11, L51, L650

Equivalent Units of Production in Unit Cost Calculation for Fair Pricing of Pharmaceuticals: A Scoping Review Protocol

Introduction

Much has already been discussed in literature on pharmaceutical pricing but very little if any on underlying unit cost function. Because regardless of pricing orientation, Drury (2021) asserts that 'the pricing decision will be influenced by the cost of the product' (p.238); which also 'provides the initial approximation of the selling price'(p.242). Moreover, Kato (1993, p.295), holds that a firm's cost level is an important determinant of its competitive position. Therefore, such information will promote transparency and assist consumers, policy makers and regulators in negotiations.

The first study on determining factors for a typical choice of cost-plus pricing in manufacturing firms was by Drury & Tayles (2005). Their search revealed only three prior studies on cost plus pricing. From 2005- 2022, four more studies were added bringing to seven in total but non on pharmaceutical industry despite the clamor against rising high prices. Another survey by Drury & Tayles (2006) indicated that sixty percent of respondents used cost-plus pricing in their organizations (Drury, p.247). Drury (2021, p.247) moreover found that 85% of those organizations used full cost while 15% used direct cost as the pricing base. Furthermore, another survey on factors that influence importance of cost-plus pricing by Guilding, Drury & Tayles (2005) found out that competition intensity significantly influence the importance of cost-plus pricing (Drury,2021:247). Similarly, Dekker and Smidt (2003) from their survey of 32 Dutch firms on the use of costing practices reported 19 of the firms to have used target costing under a different name (Drury,2021:247).

Equivalent units constitute the equivalence of completed units in work in progress needed to complete the denominator for dividing total production cost to obtain unit production cost /quotient. The denominator is also known as equivalent production. This is the management accounting convention for continuous process costing for manufacturing of homogenous products. Equivalent production without equivalent units overstates the unit production cost and by extension unit selling price. This is the theory the study seeks to verify.

Furthermore, between 1964 and date only four studies have been conducted on equivalent units costing. Three of those studies have been on pedagogy (De Coster,1964; Buchheit, et al.,2002; Guerreiro, et al,2006; Kelly and Shoemaker,2018) while the last was an empirical study on determining completion rate for equivalent units calculation theoretically compared to practice (Guerreiro, et al,2006). De Coster,1964 examines implication of inventory valuation methods on equivalent units of production calculation. Buchheit et al (2002) investigated time-based approach versus the traditional rule-based approach. Results showed students' preference for time- based approach. Finally, Kelly and Shoemaker (2018) explored simulation method to clarify and enhance students 'understanding of equivalent units of production.

Furthermore, various studies have been conducted on fair pricing with 'fair' being very contentious. In auditing fair concept is associated with objectivity and verifiability. Hence, we define fair pricing as the price that is based on a verifiable cost function. Consequently, we equate

Equivalent Units of Production in Unit Cost Calculation for Fair Pricing of Pharmaceuticals: A Scoping Review Protocol

fair pricing with cost-plus pricing method being the offshoot of process costing obtained by marking up unit cost of goods sold with appropriate profit margin.

Consistent results from Tomas Bata University database, Connected Papers, Web of Science, Science Direct, Google Scholar and JBI Evidence Synthesis have shown no review with similar title. No study has been conducted on inclusion and importance of equivalent unit in unit production cost function as a basis for setting prices for pharmaceuticals; structure of pharmaceutical firms' unit cost function and motivation for choice of pricing methods. W.H.O. defines Cost-plus pricing as “the pricing practice for setting the price of pharmaceutical products that considers the manufacturing costs, costs of R&D, costs associated with regulatory processes and compliance, overhead and other operational expenses, and a profit to determine a price.” Despite the method's adoption in Australia and Japan, it however suggests against the method until there is a mandatory and transparent reporting of cost components including accessibility to R&D costs required for setting prices. Other constraints to full adoption include complexity of cost structures and lack of agreement on the methodology for determining and reporting costs related to R&D in the pharmaceutical industry. This scenario reveals gaps and a call for studies on cost-plus pricing method, cost minimization and fair pricing. Moreover, a systematic review commissioned by W.H.O. did not yield satisfactory result because no study met the inclusion criteria of the systematic review. It however acknowledges “the increasing policy interests and current technical work by various stakeholders in developing a validated framework for setting pharmaceutical prices based on cost inputs.”

Considering the importance of unit cost in setting (fair) prices, the objective of this scoping review is to assess the extent of the literature on equivalent units production, unit cost function and fair pricing in the pharmaceutical industry. Furthermore, choice of a scoping review is justified on the grounds of expert recommendation and systematic review results on cost-plus pricing by W.H.O. According to Arksey and O'Malley (2005), scoping review can be undertaken as ‘standalone projects in their own right, especially where an area is complex or has not been reviewed comprehensively before’. It can also be used as a research synthesis “to map the body of literature on a particular topic or research area and provide an opportunity to identify key concepts; gaps in the research; and types and sources of evidence to inform practice, policymaking, and research” (Pham,2014). Munn et al. (2018) posit that “Scoping reviews can be conducted to identify and examine characteristics or factors related to a particular concept in papers or studies, and in the mapping, reporting or discussion of these characteristics/concepts.” In this study there are three concepts of interest which need clarification: equivalent units costing, unit cost function and fair pricing of pharmaceuticals”. Moreover, in W.H.O. commissioned systematic review on cost-plus pricing, “no study met inclusion criteria” (W.H.O. Report ,2021). Against this background, scoping reviews are first needed on key concepts to build the necessary critical mass for follow up systematic review or empirical studies.

Review questions

i) How is cost per unit determined for fair pricing of medicines in the pharmaceutical industry?

Equivalent Units of Production in Unit Cost Calculation for Fair Pricing of Pharmaceuticals: A Scoping Review Protocol

- ii) What constitutes unit cost in pharmaceutical pricing given different pricing methods?
- iii) Does unit cost count in pricing decisions in pharmaceutical industry?
- iv) Is fair pricing feasible in the pharmaceutical industry?
- v) What is fair pricing in the pharmaceutical industry?

Keywords

Equivalent units production; fair pricing; pharmaceuticals; unit cost function

Inclusion criteria

Participants

This review will consider studies on cost per unit based on process costing, fair pricing for the purpose of definition regardless of context, pricing methods in the pharmaceutical industry, and equivalent units production.

Concept

This review will consider studies that explore the concepts of equivalent units costing, unit cost function and fair pricing of pharmaceuticals.

Context

Pharmaceutical firms in the Eurozone constitute the context. Firms include both international and national in terms of ownership. Manufacturing of organic and generic medicines are included. Merchandizing, bulk breaking activities and pharmacies are excluded. We intend to generalize with Eurozone experience.

Types of sources

This scoping review will consider relevant quantitative, qualitative and mixed study designs on equivalent units, unit costing and fair pricing of manufactured medicines.

Qualitative studies will also be considered that focus on qualitative data including, but not limited to, designs such as phenomenology, grounded theory, qualitative description, if any. In addition, systematic reviews that meet the inclusion criteria will also be considered. Text and opinion papers will also be considered for inclusion in this scoping review.

Equivalent Units of Production in Unit Cost Calculation for Fair Pricing of Pharmaceuticals: A Scoping Review Protocol

Methods

The proposed scoping review will be conducted in accordance with the JBI methodology for scoping reviews (Peters, et al,2015).

Search strategy

The search approach will target both published and unpublished studies. An initial restricted search of Google Scholar was conducted to discover papers on the topic. The text words contained in the titles and abstracts of relevant articles, as well as the index terms used to describe the articles, were utilized to develop a thorough search strategy for selected electronic databases (see Appendix I). The search strategy, including all identified keywords and index terms, will be tailored to each included information source. The reference lists of papers selected for full-text review will be screened for additional studies. Electronic searches in English language will be conducted on Google Scholar, Scopus, Science Direct and Web of Science.

Study/Source of evidence selection

Following the search, all identified citations will be collated and uploaded into Zotero Reference Manager and duplicates removed. Following a pilot test, titles and abstracts will then be screened by two or more independent reviewers for assessment against the inclusion criteria for the review. Potentially relevant sources will be retrieved in full and their citation details imported into the JBI System for the Unified Management, Assessment and Review of Information (JBI SUMARI) (JBI, Adelaide, Australia). The full text of selected citations will be assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria by two or more independent reviewers. Reasons for exclusion of sources of evidence at full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer/s. The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final scoping review and presented in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses extension for scoping review (PRISMA-ScR) flow diagram.

Data extraction

Two independent reviewers will use a customized data extraction tool designed by the reviewers to retrieve data from studies included in the scoping review. There is a draft extraction form provided in (Appendix II). The following study characteristics will be analyzed and recorded: author(s); year of publication; citation information; origin (country); type of literature (research [include if thesis] or policy document); aim/purpose; design/methods; study population; concept and how concept was defined; and, industry (pharmaceuticals, manufacturing, etc.). During the data extraction process, the draft data extraction tool will be changed and modified as necessary.

Equivalent Units of Production in Unit Cost Calculation for Fair Pricing of Pharmaceuticals: A Scoping Review Protocol

The scoping review will detail the modifications in detail. Any disagreements among the reviewers will be resolved through discussion or with the assistance of an additional reviewer. If necessary, authors of papers will be contacted to request missing or extra data. (texts) and numbers (frequency) will be utilized to extract both quantitative and qualitative data.

Data analysis and presentation

The extracted data will be quantitatively analyzed using frequencies and counts. Descriptive content analysis will be used to evaluate textual data from qualitative studies. Graphs, charts, and narratives will be used to present the results.

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Declarations

Corresponding author is an expert academic with over two decades of cognate industry experience of which ten years relate to teaching accounting courses including management accounting.

Author contributions

SU designed the overall analysis and wrote the protocol while AI reviewed and provided methodological guidance. SU conducted the preliminary search and used the results to refine search criteria.

Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this project.

Equivalent Units of Production in Unit Cost Calculation for Fair Pricing of Pharmaceuticals: A Scoping Review Protocol

References

- Arksey H, O'Malley L. Scoping studies: Towards a methodological framework. *Int J Soc Res Methodol Theory Pract.* 2005;8(1):19–32. 22.
- Broekhof, M. (2002). Transparency in the pharmaceutical industry - A cost accounting approach to the prices of drugs, University of Groningen.
- Braun V, Clarke V. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual Res Psychol.* 2006;3(2):77–101.
- Buchheit, S., Collins, D. and Reitenga, A. (2002). A Note on Equivalent Units Calculations. *Advances in Accounting Education Teaching and Curriculum Innovations.*
[https://doi.org/10.1108/S1085-4622\(2002\)0000004009](https://doi.org/10.1108/S1085-4622(2002)0000004009)
- Colquhoun HL, Levac D, O'Brien KK, Straus S, Tricco AC, Perrier L, et al. Scoping reviews: Time for clarity in definition, methods, and reporting. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2014;67(12):1291–4.
- DeCoster, D. T. (1964). The Unit Cost Denominator in Process Costing. *The Accounting Review,* 39(3), 750–754. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/242472>
- Drury, C. (2021). Cost and Management Accounting 11, CENTAGE, London
- Drury, C. and Tayles, M. (2005). Explicating the design of overhead absorption procedures in UK organizations. *British Accounting Review,*37(1),47-84
- Drury, C. and Tayles, M. (2005). Explicating the design of overhead absorption procedures in UK organizations. *British Accounting Review,*37(1),47-84
- Edwards et al (2003). “Costing, pricing and politics in the British steel industry, 1918-1967” *Management Accounting Research,* 14: 25-49.
- Green J, Thorogood N. The role of theory. In: *Qualitative Methods for Health Research;* 2018. p. 29–48.
- Guerreiro, R., Cornachione, E. B., & Catelli, A. (2006). Equivalent units of production: A new look at an old issue. *Managerial Auditing Journal,* 21(3), 303–316.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/02686900610653035>
- Guilding, C., Drury, C., and Tayles, M. (2005). An empirical investigation of the importance of cost-plus pricing. *Managerial Auditing Journal,*20(2),125-37.
- Hartling, L., Featherstone, R., Nuspl, M., Shave, K., Dryden, D.M., Vandermeer, B. (2017). Grey literature in systematic reviews: a cross-sectional study of the contribution of non-English reports, unpublished studies and dissertations to the results of meta-analyses in child-relevant reviews. *BMC Med Res Methodol.*;17(1):1–11.
- Kato, Y. (1993). Target costing support systems: lessons from leading Japanese companies, *Management Accounting Research,* March,33-48.
- Kelly, M. and Shoemaker, N. (2018). Closing Pandora's Box: Reducing Students' Confusion With A Process Costing Simulation. *Journal of Accounting and Finance,* 18(7), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.33423/jaf.v18i7.461>
- Levac D, Colquhoun H, O'Brien KK. Scoping studies: advancing the methodology. *Implement Sci.* 2010;5(69):1–9.
- Mahood Q, Dwayne VE, Irvin E. (2014). Searching for grey literature for systematic reviews: challenges and benefits. *Res Synth Methods.*;5(3):221–34.
- Peters, M.D.J., Godfrey, C.M., Khalil, H., McInerney, P., Parker D, Soares, C.B. (2015). Guidance

Equivalent Units of Production in Unit Cost Calculation for Fair Pricing of Pharmaceuticals: A Scoping Review Protocol

- for conducting systematic scoping reviews. *Int J Evid Based Healthc*;13(3):141–6.
- Pham, M.T., Rajić, A., Greig, J.D., Sargeant, J.M., Papadopoulos, A., Mcewen, S.A. (2014). A scoping review of scoping reviews: advancing the approach and enhancing the consistency. *Res Synth Methods.* ;5(4):371–85.
- Polkinghorne DE. Language and meaning: data collection in qualitative research. *J Couns Psychol.* 2005;52(2):137–45.
- Saleh A, Ratajeski M, Bertolet M. Grey literature searching for health sciences systematic reviews: a prospective study of time spent and resources utilized. *Evid Based Libr Inf Pract.* 2014;9(3):28–50.
- Schreyögg, et al., (2006). Cost accounting to determine prices: How well do prices reflect costs in the German DRG-system? *Health Care Management Science* **volume 9**, pages269–279
- Skinner, R. (1970). The Determination of Selling Prices. *Journal of Industrial Economics*,
- Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. (2018). PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): checklist and explanation. *Ann Intern Med.*;169(7):467–73.
- World Health Organization (2020). W.H.O Guideline on Country Pharmaceutical Pricing Policies. ACCESS TO MEDICINES AND HEALTH PRODUCTS.

Appendices

Appendix I: Search strategy

Search terms used were: Unit cost of medicine /, cost per unit/, fair pricing/, and fair price of medicines/ will be subject headings, while relevant keywords will include medicine*, drugs*, and pharmaceuticals*.

Web of Science

January- September,2022

Search statement	Search terms	Results retrieved	Included	Journal	Topic
	Manufacturing costs of pharmaceutical companies		1	J Pharm Innov (2008) 3:30–40 DOI 10.1007/s12247-008-9024-4	Analysis of Manufacturing Costs in Pharmaceutical Companies
	cost per unit of medicine				
	fair pricing				
	fair price of medicines				
	cost per unit of medicine				
	cost per unit of pharmaceuticals				
	cost per unit of drugs	143		AIDS	
	Production costs of drugs				Examining the production costs of antiretroviral drugs <i>AIDS.</i> 20(13):1745-1752, August 22, 2006.
	<i>antiretroviral drugs</i> , <i>production cost</i> , <i>price</i> , <i>active pharmaceutical ingredients</i> , <i>Brazil</i>				
	production cost of medicines			BMJ Global Health	Estimated costs of production and potential prices for the WHO Essential Medicines List

Equivalent Units of Production in Unit Cost Calculation for Fair Pricing of Pharmaceuticals: A Scoping Review Protocol

Appendix II: Data extraction instrument

Reviewer: _____

Date : _____

Information to be extracted	
Author(s)	
Year of publication	
Citation information	
Origin (country)	
Type of literature (research [include if thesis] or policy document)	
Aim/purpose	
Design/methods	
Study population	
Concept	
How concept was defined	
Industry (pharmaceuticals, manufacturing, etc.)	